

Optical Sensing Using Fiber Bragg Gratings: Fundamentals & Applications

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In this article Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) technology used to implement fiber sensors is explained and some applications in temperature and strain measurements are presented. In the first section the fundamentals and operation principles of FBGs are shown as well as optical fiber sensing interrogators. The second part of the article presents applications in temperature measurements in power transmission lines, shrinkage measurements in concrete structures and spatiotemporal variations of temperature in groundwater - surface water.

FBGs have been used, over the last few years, for a wide variety of sensing applications including: monitoring of civil structures, such as highways, bridges, buildings, dams, etc. Remote sensing in oil wells, power cables, pipelines, space stations, etc. Smart structures such as, airplane wings, ship hulls, buildings, sports equipment, etc., as well as traditional strain, pressure and temperature sensing [1].

FBG sensors have some advantages over conventional electrical-sensors due to the intrinsic properties of optical fibers. These devices perform a direct transformation of the sensed parameter to optical wavelength, independent of light levels, connectors or fiber losses maintaining some advantages such as:

- High electrical isolation, providing immunity to electromagnetic interference.
- Total passivity (i.e. no resistive heating).
- Small size, allowing be easily embedded or laminated.

- Possibility of multiplexing several sensors in one optical fiber.
- Environmentally more stable (comparing glass to copper).
- Capability of monitoring sensors over long distances.

In addition, FBG's have the potential for a very low cost due to device simplicity and high volume telecommunication usage. These properties confer to FBG sensors a special interest for scientists and engineers that are looking for alternatives to conventional sensors [1].

Principle of Operation of the FBG Sensing Technology

A FBG sensor is a wavelength-dependent filter/reflector formed by introducing a periodic perturbation of the refractive index within the core of an optical fiber.

When a broad-spectrum light is launched into a fiber with a FBG sensor, a portion of its energy will be transmitted through, and another portion will be reflected for a particular wavelength, named the Bragg wavelength (λ_B), which satisfies the Bragg condition (*i.e.* $\lambda_B = 2\eta_{eff}\Lambda$). Then, the principle of sensing using a FBG sensor is based on the fact that both the effective refraction index (η_{eff}), as well as the periodic spacing between the grating planes (Λ), is affected by external perturbations such as strain and temperature, inducing a shift in the reflected wavelength. This principle is depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Transmission and reflection spectra of a Fiber Bragg Grating sensor

Exposing the fiber with the FBG to a temperature change (ΔT) or stretching/compressing it (Δl) will spectrally shift ($\Delta \lambda_B$) proportionally to the external action. In this case, the Bragg wavelength dependency on the temperature and strain could be described by:

$$\Delta \lambda_B = 2 \left(\eta_{eff} \frac{d\lambda}{dT} + \lambda \frac{d\eta_{eff}}{dT} \right) \Delta T + 2 \left(\eta_{eff} \frac{d\lambda}{dl} + \lambda \frac{d\eta_{eff}}{dl} \right) \Delta l \quad (1)$$

The first term in equation (1) represents the strain effect and the second term represents the effect of temperature on the FBG sensor. Typically, the fractional wavelength change in λ_B is of the order of 10pm/°C and 1.2pm per microstrain (i.e. 12nm for 1% strain) [1]. Depending on the system instrumentation used to demodulate the wavelength shift, a FBG sensor can be used to detect both static and dynamic changes. Some schemes developed to implement these systems are explained hereafter.

Optical Sensing Interrogators

The Bragg wavelength is measured by detecting the wavelength reflected by the FBG sensor in order to measure physical variables. The measurement of the reflected wavelength is made by an Optical Sensing Interrogation System that integrates both electronic and optical devices. Furthermore, the system finds the value of the variables measured, by processing the information obtained of the wavelength shift [2].

An Optical Sensing Interrogation System is composed of three main blocks: the emitter block, the peak detection block and the data acquisition block. Depending on the configuration of each block, it is possible to have different interrogation schemes. In this article are presented two system implementations that were selected due to their characteristics of acceptable resolution, low cost of the system components, ease of selection of the acquisition rate and simplicity of implementation [2].

The first one is the Edge Filter Interrogation Scheme. In this kind of systems, an edge filter is used in order to obtain the output signal power as a function of the central wavelength of the peak. A block diagram is shown in Figure 2.a. In this system, a broadband light source is used.

The circulator directs the beam to the FBG sensor that reflects a particular wavelength that is directed again by the circulator to the peak detection block. The detection block has a splitter that divides the power of the reflected peak. The coupling ratio of the splitter is selected depending on the losses of the system and the range of power detected by the receivers. The highest power output of the splitter is treated using an edge filter while the lowest power signal is taken as the reference signal. The filter output signal power is a function of the central wavelength of the peak. Both, the reference signal and the filtered signal, are detected by two individual receivers. The receiver output currents are compared in order to obtain the central wavelength of the peak using the ratio between these two variables [2].

The second FBG interrogation implementation is depicted in Figure 2b. The system is composed of a broadband source, an optical circulator, two FBGs and the Data Acquisition Block. One of the FBGs is used as a reference (FBGR) and it is placed on a controlled environment, the other FBG is used for the measurement (FBGM) and it is exposed to the environment changes. Finally in the Data Acquisition Block the transmitted signal of the reference FBG is characterized. The broadband source can be implemented using a Fabry Pérot laser that emits an optical signal that flows through the fiber until the circulator, then the optical signal cross through the second port of the circulator and finds the first FBG, FBGM. This FBGM reflects a signal at a particular frequency, this signal flows again through the circulator to the third port, where it finds the reference FBG, FBGR. In this system, the signal analyzed is the transmitted signal, which corresponds to the reflected signal of the sensing FBGM, filtered with the central wavelength of the reference FBG (FBGR). Then, the data acquisition block uses the optical power of this signal to give a corresponding measurement of temperature, strain or the desire variable to characterize [3].

When the two FBGs are in the exact same conditions, if both sensors had the same central wavelength, the filtering process cause the signal to lost most of its power. As the sensing FBG starts to change due to any external perturbation, the Bragg wavelength begins to move, with this change, the filtered portion starts to change, giving different values of optical power to the data acquisition block [3].

Figure 2. Block diagram for (a) edge filter interrogation scheme and (b) double FBG interrogation scheme [2][3].

Applications

This section presents some applications of FBG sensors that show the interest and benefits of the technology.

Temperature measurements in power transmission lines using FBGs

In overhead power transmission lines, one constraint for power transmission capacity is the conductor temperature, when temperature increases it causes the elongation of the line which means a SAG increase and therefore a reduction of the distance between the conductor and the nearby objects (ground clearance)[4] (Figure 3a). Moreover, operating transmission lines at high temperatures causes permanent changes on the conductor length called creep and a premature aging due to a permanent change on the crystalline structure of the conductor material known as annealing, that decreases rupture strain and increase failure probabilities [5].

Fig. 3. (a) Temperature measurement set-up in an overhead line and (b) the obtained results.

Estimating the temperature of an overhead power transmission line conductor from the current is a complex problem. This is due to the interaction of several variables such as wind direction, humidity, solar radiation, environmental temperature, among others that vary through the line because of, for instance, air disturbances caused by near objects, creating hot spots in the line that limit the overall capacity of the network and increase failure probabilities [6]. For those reasons, power transmission lines are traditionally rated under worst weather conditions to guarantee that the conductor temperature will not increase over a maximum allowed. Nevertheless those conditions are rarely present and in a few cases the temperature rises over the maximum at which the line was rated, with the supposed weather conditions making the transmission line less efficient and less reliable [6].

Motivated by an increase in demand from users, the difficulty to install new lines and the need to transport additional and sporadic amounts of energy from renewable energy sources, or to overcome emergency situations and in order to obtain higher efficiency in overhead transmission lines there have been proposed and tested a variety of methods that take into account the different factors that affect conductor temperature and calculate line capacity dynamically [7]. One possibility is to use FBG sensors in order to do temperature and strain measurements. In an experiment realized at Universidad Nacional de Colombia, a fiber optic with one FBG sensor in it was attached to an overhead transmission line in order to measure temperature in the midpoint of the line as shown in Fig. 3a. The package of the FBG sensor consists of a copper tube in which the sensor was introduced so as to avoid the effects of strain in the sensor and then the measurements were performed in two stages, in the first one, measurements were carried out with no electric energy in the line, allowing determine temperature variations in sun and shadow periods. In the second stage, the line was energized with two different current values. The results are shown in Fig. 3b where temperature variations can be seen as the result of the current flowing through the line and because of the weather conditions, mostly the cooling effect of the wind, evidencing in this way the viability for implement a smart administration of power networks by using optical fiber sensors.

Shrinkage Measurements in Concrete Structures

Measuring the impact of shrinkage on concrete structures has been an important case of study for civil engineers, not only because it is directly related with the creation of fissures that damages

the structures, but also because it is a phenomenon in which most of their causes are unknown. Parameters like relative humidity, solar radiation, the volume and form of the structure interfere on this process, however, it is unknown the exact effect on shrinkage of each one of these variables [8].

There are multiple elements that can be used to monitor the state of concrete [8]. One of them are FBG sensors, they have multiple advantages like their small dimensions, allowing them to be inserted into the concrete beam without creating any structural deformation, their high sensitivity and linearity, which are not affected by the electromagnetic interference, and finally their inherited sensitivity to temperature and strain giving simultaneous measurements of both variables [2]. With this kind of sensors, it could be possible to monitor the dynamic behavior during the curing process of the material, even when it is fresh, opening the possibility to act on mitigating the effects of shrinkage.

In practice to measure shrinkage, FBG sensors are used in pairs near each other, with one of them isolated from strain to sense only temperature in order to have a temperature compensation. However, it is possible to use a two bare FBG arrangement that will allow to obtain the strain and temperature profiles separately from the same measurement, removing the need of temperature or strain compensation in such test [9].

The experimental setup is presented on Figure 4. A concrete beam is placed inside a semi-adiabatic chamber to ensure that the inside-beam temperature behavior is mainly governed by the reactions between the mixture components, then, two FBG sensors, with different temperature and strain sensitivities, are inserted inside this beam at the same point. The central wavelength of the sensors is tracked using a FBG Interrogator to perform post-experimental data processing. Both sensors yield on a 2x2 equations system, which could be solved with the exact values of sensitivities of each sensor. An extra sensor is placed to monitor the room temperature inside the semi-adiabatic chamber

Figure 4. Experimental Setup for the two-bare-FBG measurement technique.

To guarantee that the measured profile belongs to the behavior of the internal reactions of the mixture, it is necessary to design an experimental setup to ensure repeatability in subsequent measurements. First, sand, cement and water are measured to adjust the correct proportions of each one in the mixture. It is known that variations on the proportion of those components in the mixture, yield on variations on the reaction that occurs. For example, for mixtures with a higher proportion between water and cement would heat even more than its opposite, and that a drier mixture would benefit retraction. A mixture with a 2:1:1.5 proportion mixture was selected (sand:cement:water), sand and cement are initially mixed until being fully incorporated. Finally, the mixture is activated by adding the water to the mixture of sand and cement, this is mixed again until the mixture has a uniform texture.

The next stage consist on the correct accommodation of the FBG bare sensors on the mixture. A circular pot with two opposite holes is placed inside the semi-adiabatic chamber, each one of the holes will house one tube to guide the sensor inside and outside the chamber. One half of the pot is filled with the concrete mixture, this would serve as a bed for the sensors, and would allow to place them in the correct position. Once both sensors are placed on their ideal positions, the other half of the pot is filled with the mixture and sieved until being sure that all the mixture inside the pot is homogeneously distributed. As last step the chamber is close, despite this, it is necessary to wait two minutes to let the inside temperature of the chamber to stabilize, after this two minutes, measurements of the center wavelengths of the sensors could be performed.

The first measurements were done with a two hours window of observation; the experimental setup previously described was applied in subsequent measurements. After data processing,

results shown that at least the temperature profile in this interval was repeatable. In this first two hours the temperature effect was also dominant over the shrinkage profile, this was proven with the temperature sensor inside the chamber because it experienced also the same heating as the inside-beam sensors [9].

In order to visualize the effect of shrinkage on the mixture, it was necessary to increase the time window of the experiment, first in two more hours, yielding on a 4 hours-time window.

Measurements were done with two different sensor accommodations, with one or two of their ends fixed to the mixture. It was determined that better results were achieved with the two-end fixed configuration, because in this case, the shrinkage profile obtained from the equations system solution was similar for both FBG sensors [10]. More measurements but with a wider time window are being performed.

Spatiotemporal variations of temperature in groundwater - surface water using fiber Bragg grating sensors

The hyporheic zones are uncertain interfaces between groundwater and surface water areas, as illustrated in Fig. 5 [11]. These zones have revealed to be active transition areas between adjacent ecological environments, which provides a number of ecological properties and services, including:

- Providing an important zone for the cycling of carbon, energy and nutrients.
- Controlling the flux and location of water exchange between stream and underground.
- Providing a rooting zone for aquatic plants.
- Providing a sink/source of sediment within a river channel.
- Providing a habitat for benthic and interstitial organisms.
- Providing a spawning ground and refuge for certain species of fish.
- Providing a natural attenuation zone for certain pollutants by biodegradation, sorption and mixing.
- Moderating river water temperature.

These important characteristics are leaving to a grown interest in the understanding of the ecosystem functionality by studying the groundwater - surface water (GW-SW) interactions.

Figure 5. Representation of GW-SW interface and hyporheic zone illustrating the setup for measure the temperature gradient.

Hyporheic zone is often characterized by complex chemical and temperature gradients, influenced by some factors such as climate and geology, which exert control on the behavior of organisms, chemicals or nutrients. In the literature, several methods to measure the interactions between GW-SW have been proposed, including hydraulic gradient measurement using a piezoelectric, conservative tracer experiments and differential discharge gauging. However, these methods do not work properly for the spatial and temporal measurements [12].

Due to the reasons mentioned above, other kind of methods must be implemented to measure spatiotemporal variations of temperature gradient between GW-SW. In our case, the use of a FBG sensor network for measuring the spatiotemporal variations of temperature through the hyporheic zone is currently explored. The planned experimental setup is shown schematically in Fig. 5. In this design, the FBG sensors are located in the hyporheic zone each 2 meters, in order to capture typical gradients of temperature for these systems [12] and as a reference; there are sensors also in the surface water located just above of the sensors in the hyporheic zone. The fiber is placed over 10 meters of the stream to cover the total area of interest in a local river. The measurement changes of temperature in surface water and hyporheic zone must be saved for 24 hours in order to collect enough data to determine the GW-SW interactions. The corresponding results are currently under evaluation.

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